

Jailolo Bay Festival As A Model For Developing Cultural Tourism In West Halmahera

Abdul Halil Hi. Ibrahim, Muhlis Hafel, Iryani S. Lamasi

Abstract: The purpose of this study was to analyze and describe the Strategy for the Implementation of the Jailolo Bay Festival conducted by the West Halmahera Tourism Office as a cultural tourism model. The design of this research method uses qualitative analysis which is a research procedure that produces descriptive data in the form of written or oral words from people and observable behaviors. Following the problems studied, illustrative study method was used. The data collection technique is carried out by interview and documentation study. The results of the research show that several implementation strategies are carried out including planning, partnership building, community capacity, and funding sources. The four stages of the success of the implementation of regional regulations (PERDA) on the Jailolo Bay Festival (FTJ) are built on all destinations so that until now Halmahera West tourism destinations continue to progress every year. Besides, with the progress of the target, it has a positive impact on the implementation of FTJ as a tourism promotion event. In 2018, FTJ entered as the top 100 national events. This achievement is the result of the work of the Tourism Office in realizing the PERDA FTJ mission. Thus, the stages of the FTJ PERDA Implementation strategy must be developed sustainably so that tourism human resources, partners, potential attractiveness, continue to be improved to give birth to West Halmahera as a friendly, safe, clean and refreshing destination for tourists. Furthermore, recommendations to the regional government of West Halmahera, especially the Department of Tourism as the executor of FTJ's tasks in realizing PERDA's mission Number: 2 of 2012 concern FTJ, is to improve the concept of implementing FTJ to suit the traditions and culture of local communities; the involvement of local communities is significant to encourage sustainable tourism, and build a Jailolo image as a motorcycle pedicab and homestay city.

Index Terms: Cultural tourism, local regulation, West Halmahera.

1 INTRODUCTION

Regional development outline is the most crucial part of the national development which is directed at developing regions and matching the rate of growth between areas in Indonesia. One regional development can be carried out with the development of tourism. Regarding tourism, this has been widely discussed in various sources, one of which is a book written by Yoeti (2008) [1] that tourism can be relied on to improve public welfare and national development. The government is trying hard to make plans and various strategies that support the progress of this sector by developing the potential of existing tourism objects as the main attraction for tourists. Tourism has now become a new industry that can make a significant contribution to the country's economic growth because it can provide employment opportunities, increase financial income, the standard of living and welfare and also activate other sectors for national foreign exchange which are needed in sustainable development. Although the global crisis has occurred several times, the number of foreign tourists traveling to various countries continues to show positive growth of 25 million people (1950), 278 million people (1980), 528 million people (1995), and continues to experience an increase of 1.1 billion people (2014) [1]. To be able to develop the quality of tourist destinations and encourage an increase in the number of foreign and domestic tourists visiting, the government is targeting that by 2019, Indonesia's tourism industry will be able to attract 20 million foreign tourists and 275 million domestic tourists. With this target, it will contribute to GDP which is 15%, foreign exchange IDR. 280 Trillion, and contribution to employment opportunities 13 million. The targets can only be realized by creating new destinations in various regions that have tourist attractions such as Bali. In 2015, the Ministry of Tourism established 10 Top Indonesian Destinations or 10 new Bali which will have an impact on increasing the number of visits and the long stay of tourists. The ten flagship destinations are; Lake Toba North Sumatra, Tanjung Kelayang Bangka Belitung, Thousand Islands DKI Jakarta, Tanjung Lesung Batam, Mandalika West Nusa Tenggara, Borobudur Central Java, Wakatobi Southeast

Sulawesi, Bromo Tengger Semeru East Java, Labuhan Bajo East Nusa Tenggara, and Morotai Island North Maluku. For the ten new destinations, the government set three priority programs that are in line with Indonesia's tourism needs, namely digitalization, airport connectivity, and tourist village homestays. These three programs are encouraged to complement attractions, accessibility and amenities in each destination, to be able to provide excellent service to tourists. The success of the target level visit achievement must be supported by all Regional Tourism Offices in Indonesia, one of which is the North Maluku Province tourism service that has compiled a strategy compiled in the Regional Tourism Development Master Plan (RIPPDA) by making Morotai Island as the primary destination and buffer destination that is Ternate, Tidore, Maba, West Halmahera, North Halmahera, and Sula Islands. Seeing his position geographically close to Morotai Islands, actually quite profitable West Halmahera because Morotai as one of Indonesia's top 10 destinations that are doing development will have a positive impact on West Halmahera. The wealth of natural and cultural potential, supported by a very strategic geographical location, the Regent of West Halmahera in 2016 determined 3 (three) superior possibilities of West Halmahera namely Agriculture, fisheries and tourism. This decision was also supported by the Regional Regulation of West Halmahera District Number 38 (2012) concerning Spatial Planning for West Halmahera in 2012-2032 that to direct development by utilizing local space in an efficient, harmonious, balanced and sustainable manner for the management of agricultural, fishery and tourism potentials for the welfare of society. In the tourism development strategy document, West Halmahera not only has a natural tourist attraction, but is also rich in cultural tourism that deserves to be known by the local, national, and even international community. Cultural tourism objects in West Halmahera include *Kedaton Sultan* Jailolo located in Soakonora Village, Banau Tomb, Old House where Government Officials Live, and Legu Dance, bamboo music, yanger, caka iba, soya-soya dance, orom sasadu ritual, rice planting rituals, traditional mutui rituals, sigofingolo, and many other cultural attractions in the community. Recognizing the

vast potential of tourism owned by West Halmahera, the local government through the tourism agency took the initiative to manage and develop the existing tourism potentials. The West Halmahera tourism industry can be said to be the front line after the agricultural and livestock sectors to increase the people economic income and the region. To be able to develop and utilize the tourism potential above with people based and sustainable, the Tourism Office in 2015 launched a village tourism development program, and in 2018 West Halmahera has 16 tourist villages. The optimism that provokes the formation of tourist villages generally comes from the belief that the potential of the attraction possessed such as nature, culture, and community tradition can attract both domestic and foreign tourists. These opportunities arise since the trend of changes in individual and group psychographic and demographic aspects tourists all over the world are shifting away from conventional types of tourism which are of a mass nature towards alternative forms of tourism that are more environmentally responsible. With the existence of tourism villages, West Halmahera has created superior tourism products that have a positive impact on community development in the future. The construction of West Halmahera as a leading tourism destination indeed requires a marketing strategy that can attract and increase the number of tourist visits. Tourism marketing by using the promotion of the Jailolo Bay Festival is also supported by the Regional Regulation (PERDA) of West Halmahera Regency No. 2 (2012) concerning the Jailolo Bay Festival (FTJ) which explains that to help the potential increase in tourism, art and culture in West Halmahera Regency to be utilized optimally, harmoniously, balanced, integrated, orderly, sustainable and to realize the creation of West Halmahera Years Visit, it is necessary to carry out promotion and marketing activities of tourism, art and culture as an annual agenda. The Jailolo Bay Festival (FTJ) has been held since 2009, and in 2018 the FTJ has entered a decade. Every year, FTJ gives its color in the promotion of West Halmahera tourism. Various diverse themes are carried on every momentum of FTJ, with the aim to explore the natural and cultural potential that exists in West Halmahera. The implementation of FTJ as this annual agenda has had an impact on the development of the tourism sector and other sectors. The attraction of West Halmahera tourism is increasingly known as one of the tourist destinations that have unique tourist attractions and steps. In 2009, was the year when the FTJ was first held as well as being the first step in the seriousness of the regional government in managing and developing the tourism potential that it has. West Halmahera Regency has unique and enchanting tourist attractions. The Jailolo Bay Festival, which has been held for ten times in the last ten years, aims to promote tourism potential, natural wealth and culture of West Halmahera Regency. The series of Jailolo Bay Festival events, all tourism potential, natural and cultural wealth, are displayed and packed with duration of approximately one week. The Jailolo Bay Festival (FTJ) event held to promote the potential of existing tourism will be maximized with the issuance of PERDA No. 2 (2012) concerning FTJ. This regulation becomes the legitimacy of the law to strengthen the noble ideals of FTJ, namely to reunite cultural diversity in one prestigious event. Since 2012, FTJ has been carried out with the spirit stated in the PERDA. Event programs, attraction readiness, and management strive to realize the mission of tourism development in western Halmahera.

2 LITERATURE REVIEW

Definition of Tourism and Festival

In anticipation of the development of the world of tourism which has globalized its nature, the Indonesian government issued Law No. 10 (2009) concerning tourism consisting of seventeen chapters and seventy articles containing provisions covering eight things, namely; 1) Tourism is a travel activity carried out by a person or group of people by visiting certain places for recreational purposes, personal development or learning the uniqueness of tourist attractions visited in a temporary period; 2) Tourists are people who travel; 3) Tourism is a variety of tourism activities and supported by various facilities and services provided by the community, entrepreneurs, the central government and regional governments; 4) Tourism is a whole activity related to tourism and is multidimensional and multidisciplinary in nature which emerges as a manifestation of the needs of each person and country and the interaction between tourists, the central government, regional governments and entrepreneurs; 5) Tourist attraction is anything that has uniqueness, beauty, and value in the form of diversity of natural wealth, culture, and man-made results that are the target or destination of tourist visits; 6) Tourism destination areas hereinafter referred to as tourism destinations are geographical areas that are in one or more administrative regions in which there are tourist attractions, public facilities, tourism facilities, accessibility, and communities that are interrelated and complement the realization of tourism; 7) Tourism business is a business that provides goods and or services to meet the needs of tourists and tourism operations; and 8) Tourism entrepreneurs are people or groups of people who carry out tourism business activities. Tourism is a phenomenon of the need for health and a change of atmosphere, a conscious assessment and growing (love) of natural beauty, especially the increasing association of various nations and classes of human society as a result of the development of commerce, industry, trade, and improvement of transportation equipment [2]. The essence of tourism is a process of temporary departure from someone or going to another place outside his residence. The encouragement of his departure was due to various interests, both because of economic, social, cultural, political, religious, health and other benefits such as just wanting to know, adding experience or learning [3]. Tourism is traveling from one place to another, is temporary, carried out by individuals or groups, as an effort to find balance or harmony and happiness with the environment in the social, cultural, natural, and scientific dimensions [4]. Tourism is a human activity that is carried out consciously that gets service alternately between people in a country itself or abroad, including the silence of people from other regions for a while seeking satisfaction that is diverse and different from what they experienced, where he gets a permanent job [5]. Whereas, the Festival can be interpreted in two senses [5], namely; 1) A happy day or week to commemorate important and historic events, people's parties; 2) Race; it can be known or concluded that the basic nature of all festivals is something related to celebrations and also the party of the people which is generally determined by something that has cultural value. The types of festivals include; a) Film Festival; It is a celebration where the contents show the production of films (usually films produced for a year); b) Music festival; Usually a series of actions in a particular place and inspired by a unifying theme, such as

national music, modern music or promoting composer/prominent works, can also take the form of contests for singers or composers; c) Art Festival; It is a big event where performances, exhibitions and competitions around the art of music, theater, painting and crafts are held; d) Cultural Festival; Cultural festivals are expressions of views on cultural, social and political issues. Often the debate changes in the focus of polarization between proponents of change and those who want to preserve "traditional" or "local culture of modernization and globalization. From the types of festivals above, it can be concluded that the Jailolo Bay Festival is included in the category of Art and Culture Festival. Organizing a festival can help in building the image of a destination as well as to attract visitors to an area. Meanwhile, Jailolo is a city in the District of West Halmahera which is the center of government and has a variety of cultural and artistic wealth. The Jailolo Bay Festival takes place in along the Jailolo Bay region. The area that has always been the center of Jailolo City, the center of trade, and the economy.

Cultural Tourism

Cultural tourism is one of the tourism sectors that has been developed by regional governments lately. Cultural tourism is one type of tourism that makes culture a significant attraction. Where in this cultural tourism tourists will be guided to recognize and understand the culture and wisdom of the local community? Besides, visitors will be spoiled with views, historical places as well as museums, representation of values and living systems of local communities, art (both performing arts and other arts), as well as culinary specialties from the indigenous or local communities concerned [6]. While Goeldner [7] argued that cultural tourism encompasses all aspects of the journey to learn from each other's lifestyles and thoughts. This definition is more directed to the destination of visitors / or tourists visiting more cultural tourism to understand the nature and compare it with the cultural conditions that it has as a new understanding, of course, in addition to the aesthetic values contained therein. Sillberberg defines cultural tourism as a visit of people from outside the destination who are driven by interest in objects or historical heritage, art, science with a lifestyle that is owned by groups, communities, regions or institutions [3]. Whereas Pendi (1999) [2] defines cultural tourism as tourism that has cultural aspects/values regarding the customs of society, religious traditions, and cultural heritage of a region. Cultural tourism is closely related to cultural tourism attractions. Elucidation of Article 14 Paragraph (1) letter b of the National Tourism Development Master Plan (RIPPARNAS) explains that cultural tourism attraction is a tourist attraction in the form of human creativity, taste and intentions as social beings. Cultural tourism attractions are divided into two cultural tourism objects that are tangible and cultural tourism objects that are intangible. Aspects included in the objects of cultural tourism include [5], such as: the existence of birth ceremonies, traditional dances, traditional music, marriage, traditional clothing (traditional clothing), various ceremonies (such as going to the fields and harvesting ceremonies), historic buildings, cultural heritage, some traditional relics, traditional fabrics (such as woven fabrics), cast of cultural festivals and classical performances, local textile products, historical and cultural museums, and other local customs. The scope of cultural tourism objects is thus comprehensive, but naturally, it can be said that these cultural tourism sites come from what people think, feel, and

do as the owner of culture as the identity of a particular culture that appears in the artefact, idea fact, and sociofact. Such cultural tourism is very attractive for tourists who are outside, so this becomes a potential and unique attraction if it can be packaged properly so that lately cultural tourism in Indonesia is overgrowing in each region. According to Mc.Kercher and du Cros [2] that the development of cultural tourism is closely related to the appreciation of the community to continuously maintain and maintain their cultural assets or cultural heritage which in their current growth is felt to be reduced. The expert then outlines that in basically, cultural tourism has at least four elements, such as tourism, how to use these cultural assets, consumption of products/works, and cultural tourists themselves. These four elements need to be further analyzed to emphasize how public services are formed to develop the four fundamental aspects of cultural tourism. In general, the three sources of the emergence of cultural tourism indeed generate different appreciation from visitors/tourists. The attraction of cultural tourism originating from socio-cultural and historical conditions so far seems to attract tourists more than those arising from religion. Particularly those that originate from historical tourism are not only to satisfy curiosity but also as part of developing insight and knowledge.

Tourism Marketing Strategy Implementation Theory

Starting from the first theory above about the concept of policy and implementation, then in this second theory, researchers used the theory of marketing strategy implementation formulated by Kotler [8] to facilitate how PERDA No. 2 (2012) as a legal product and policy product implemented in a regional tourism agenda namely tourism promotion agenda with FTJ strategy. Tourism marketing implementation involves all components to carry out marketing strategies successfully; determine the organizational structure, form practical strategy, skills, policies, systems, incentives, effective communication, and the most appropriate organizational goals. Even though each of these factors can change because of a new strategy, each must be determined as part of the implementation process. Tourism marketing plays an important role in the success or failure of tourism and influences the level of impact in the local community. Four aspects that can explain the success rate of implementing tourism policies are; 1) Planning, a comprehensive process that ranges from having a strategic plan for all tourism marketing. Tourism marketing initiatives must focus on strategies that are agreed upon and understood by all stakeholders, especially local communities, working in existing social structures even though this can be challenging. Part of strategic planning must also create a healthy business plan for the company; 2) Partnerships, the need to develop partnerships to increase the benefits of tourism for the poor is at the core of the tourism agenda. The partnership is an agreement to cooperate in fulfilling obligations or carrying out specific tasks by carrying out resources and various risks and benefits. Partnerships between communities and the private sector, government and donor agencies or NGOs can all produce benefits for tourism marketing; 3) Community capacity, Tourism marketing must involve the community. Community capacity plays an important role in the level of success in tourism marketing. Community capacity is seen in four aspects, namely; 1) the availability of tourism potential in the community is a crucial component in the development of tourism products; 2) the availability of community involvement in the development of the tourism sector; 3) understanding the

existing skills in the community is very important in assessing the capacity of the community to deliver and identify capacity building needs; and 4) availability of funds, the availability of natural and cultural resources that have tourism value also requires the availability of funds in developing the potential and promotion and marketing of tourism. Tourism generally assumes economic growth expectations, and these expectations encourage the tourism industry to develop and succeed in the implementation of best practices in the tourism industry. There are at least three crucial aspects in tourism marketing implementation; a) marketers must have continuity in conducting tourism marketing; b) integration of the direction of tourism development; c) the implementation shows the relationship between the basic principles of tourism marketing and the value of its strategy in responding to the challenges of tourism marketing that continues to grow with a combination of the formulation of marketing-segmentation strategy, targeting, positioning, and marketing programs (products, prices, places, and promotions) can be implemented by marketers in relation to brand innovation efforts, consumer trust and the development of new market opportunities; d) Implementation with various best practices can guide the implementation of tourism business activities that can balance economic, community, social, cultural and environmental interests. Institutional implementation will position the roles and responsibilities of stakeholders in driving the overall marketing dynamics. This implementation is an internalization of marketing principles and coordination of synergies between stakeholders; e) control and evaluation are needed to ensure that various instruments and carrying capacity used in the tourism business can go as they should, including in developing the required potential to boost tourism activities that are not only beneficial for the present interests but also beneficial for long-term investments.

3 RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This research design includes a type of qualitative research with a focus on the study of PERDA No. 2 (2012) implementation concerning FTJ at the West Halmahera Tourism Office (Case Study on the Development of a Cultural Tourism Implementation Program). Qualitative research emphasizes inductive analysis, not deductive analysis. The data collected is not intended to support or reject the hypotheses that have been prepared before the study begins, but the abstractions are arranged as specificities that have been received and grouped through a data collection process that has been carefully carried out [8]. This research will be carried out in the District Tourism Office. West Halmahera as the executor of the Jailolo Bay Festival duties and also the party making the Planning and Implementation of the FTJ PERDA to the construction of the destination. The most important data or information to be collected and reviewed in this study is mostly in the form of qualitative data. The data will be extracted from various data sources, and the types of data sources that will be used in this study include the informant or resource person, the place and events or activities carried out related to the implementation of the FTJ PERDA, and official files or documents as supporting data that can clarify the primary data. Furthermore, the data is collected through observation, interviews, and documentation techniques. The purpose of data analysis is to simplify data into a form that is easier to read and interpret. After the data is collected, the next step is data analysis. This study uses qualitative analysis,

including interview notes, observation notes relating to the problem under study, official data in the form of documents or archives, memoranda in the data collection process and also all views obtained from anywhere and recorded. The analysis is not intended to prove a prediction or research hypothesis, but all conclusions made up to theories that may be developed are formed from all data that has been successfully found and collected in the field. The nature of inductive analysis strongly emphasizes the importance of what happens and is found in the field which is based explicitly on the characteristics of the context in its natural conditions. In the process of qualitative analysis, according to Miles & Huberman, three main components must be genuinely understood [10], namely:

a. Data Reduction

Data reduction is the first component in the analysis which is a process of selection, focusing, simplification, and abstraction of all types of information written in full in the field notes. This process continues as long as a qualitative-oriented project takes place. Data reduction is part of the analysis process that reinforces, shortens, makes focus, discards insignificant things and arranges data in such a way that the data presentation narratives and conclusions from the problem units that have been studied in the research can be done.

b. Data Presentation

Data presentation is an organization of information assemblies, a description in the form of a complete narrative that further enables the conclusions of research to be carried out. Data presentation is a narrative about various things that occur or are found in the field, thus allowing the researcher to do something about the analysis or other actions based on his understanding. Data presentation in addition to the form of sentence narratives can also include various types of matrices, drawings/schemes, work networks related to activities, and even tables as supporting the narrative.

c. Conclusions and Verification

The conclusion is the result of qualitative research. Findings need to be verified to be sufficiently robust and genuinely accountable. The process of analysis in qualitative research, specifically the activities are carried out inductively, interactively from each data unit, together with the process of implementing data collection, and with the cycle process. This study uses an interactive analysis model (Interactive Model of Analysis). The researcher moves between the four "axes" of the coil during data collection, then steps back and forth between data reduction activities, data presentation and concluding.

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

FTJ Cultural Tourism Implementation Strategy

PERDA Implementation Number: 2 of 2012 concerning FTJ implemented by the West Halmahera Tourism Office in realizing West Halmahera as a tourist destination, requires the support of resources, both institutionally, infrastructure and financial. First, the institutional structure of the West Halmahera Tourism Office hierarchically consists of the Head of Service, Secretary, Destination Development, Promotion and Marketing, Tourism Development, Art and Culture Tradition. Second, the facilities and infrastructure owned by the West Halmahera Tourism Office for organizing FTJ

internally and externally are sufficiently supportive. Third, financial support for West Halmahera tourism affairs comes from the Regional Budget (APBD) of West Halmahera and the APBN Budget. Thus, regarding funding support, it is very adequate to support the successful implementation of tourism development and the implementation of the Jailolo Bay Festival (FTJ). The form of implementation or implementation of the strategy that has been established by the West Halmahera Tourism Office to realize the FTDA PERDA mission is to develop programs that support tourism development, among others; 1) improve the quality and quantity of West Halmahera tourism destinations. This strategy is implemented to maintain West Halmahera as a favorite tourist destination that has high competitiveness. The implementation of this strategy has been carried out through two programs; a) destination development program which includes the development of new leading attractions such as special interest tours, tourist villages, in addition, there are efforts to improve the facilities and infrastructure that have been implemented with the construction of roads, bridges, and provide transportation to various destinations in West Halmahera; b). tourism development program through organizing tourism events namely FTJ. Through the program, it has succeeded in enriching West Halmahera tourism products in the form of tourist villages and various other types of tourism; 2) Realizing a tourism marketing strategy that is oriented to effectiveness, efficiency and on target. This strategy is implemented to increase the attractiveness of West Halmahera tourism at national and international levels. Through this strategy, the potential and attractions of West Halmahera can be increasingly recognized by tourists. The form of strategy implementation is carried out through marketing development programs, including: market analysis for the promotion and marketing of tourism objects by conducting tourism market surveys and dialogues, increasing the use of information technology, developing a network of tourism promotion cooperation, promoting domestic and foreign tourism, making materials - promotional materials for tourism in the form of printed promotional materials, tourism CDs and others, organizing a Fam Tour involving journalists and tourism business people; 3) Optimizing various efforts to strengthen and expand the network of cooperation. This strategy is implemented to improve the institutional and HR capacity of tourism owned by the West Halmahera Tourism Office. With the collaboration formed by the activities carried out by the West Halmahera Tourism Office with other provinces, it shows that this strategy has run synergistically. The implementation of the plan is carried out through two programs, namely: partnership development programs and marketing development programs. Partnership development is carried out by facilitating FTJ implementation activities, in addition to increasing the quality and quantity of FTJ, there is also a cooperative relationship between the Tourism Office and groups or communities in West Halmahera. While the marketing development program is carried out through tourism information services carried out at TIC (Tourist Information Center). The collaboration established through this activity is a partnership between the West Halmahera Tourism Office and the provinces that align their vision in Indonesia. Several programs that have been implemented by the West Halmahera Tourism Office show that the strategies set are following the objectives and strategic objectives to be achieved. Where the success of an FTJ program cannot be

assessed immediately when the program has been implemented, a performance indicator is needed to measure the extent to which the set strategic objectives can be achieved. The following is a description of program achievements based on the goals achieved, as follows.

1. The realization of a creative and innovative culture-based tourism destination

This target indicator is the number of tourist visits to the Tourist Attraction (DTW). The number of tourists visiting West Halmahera as a tourist destination (destination) continues to increase from year to year, as shown in the table below.

Tabel 1 Number of tourist visits of 2009 – 2017

Years	Number of Visits (person)	
	foreign tourists	Domestic tourists
2009	2	435
2010	5	653
2011	11	822
2012	12	981
2013	14	1121
2014	13	1242
2015	11	1325
2016	15	1345
2017	11	932

From the table above, shows that the number of tourist visits to West Halmahera continues to increase every year. This increase is undoubtedly due to the attractiveness of FTJ which continues to evaluate the implementation concept. From this evaluation gave birth to FTJ which has more attraction under the wishes of tourists. Tourist visits which experienced a decline in 2017 were inseparable from the spirit of leadership that took place from the transfer of Fenny Kiat who served during the regent's term Namto Hui Roba to be replaced by Damianus Gate during the reign of Regent Dany Mission. This leadership shift in the Tourism Office internally also affected FTJ management in 2017. The effect of this sharpening has an impact on the level of tourist visits that have decreased.

2. The realization of effective and efficient marketing

There are two target indicators, namely the number of domestic tourists and foreign tourists. According to a survey of the number of Indonesian tourists and the number of foreign tourists has always increased every year. From Table 1, it has been shown that the number of international tourist arrivals continues to grow. The increase in foreign tourists is also inseparable from the tourist attraction of West Halmahera which continues to fascinate in the eyes of tourists.

3. The realization of the tourism industry that can move the regional economy

This target consists of 2 (two) indicators, namely indicators of the length of stay of domestic tourists and the length of stay of foreign tourists. But until now there is no data in the tourism department about the length of stay of tourists in West Halmahera. The Tourism Office should have the data because the indicators of success in tourism development are seen from the level of tourist visits, the length of stay of tourists and the level of repeat visits.

4. The realization of institutional capacity, human resources, regulations and operational mechanisms that are effective and efficient

Indicators on this target are the number of tourist villages and the number of field trip group (Pokdarwis). With the existence of tourism villages and Pokdarwis, there is an increase in support and community participation to be directly involved in the development of West Halmahera tourism. In 2015 the tourism agency formed ten tourist villages, and in 2017 there were added 2 tourism villages. In 2018 there are four tourism villages attached so that the total tourist villages in West Halmahera in 2018 are 16 tourism villages. The implementation of tourism development strategies under the mission of the regional government as well as preparing destinations for the interests of FTJ has been carried out maximally by the West Halmahera Tourism Office. Of course, evaluation is needed to improve every weakness in the implementation of the Jailolo Bay Festival.

Four Aspects of Jailolo Bay Festival Implementation (FTJ)

1. Planning

There are four stages of policy implementation, namely; planning, partnership building, community capacity and the availability of funds. At each step of the FTJ implementation every year, it always carries different themes and concepts. Concept formulation is the initial stage in the implementation of FTJ. This departs from the reality of society, culture, and the dynamics of tourism that developed in the Regency. West Halmahera. This concept was formulated by the Tourism Office as the implementer of the FTJ and presented to SKPD and the Regent of West Halmahera to ask for advice, input and questions to improve the FTJ concept. As a national event, FTJ West Halmahera highlights the unique aspects of local culture because there are seven main tribes of western Halmahera. The seven tribes provide their color in the development and dynamics of tourism culture in West Halmahera. In the 1st FTJ to the 10th FTJ, the themes carried were different from the different FTJ implementation concepts. But local culture is the main base in the concept of the PERDA Implementation. The strategy of using local culture as a basis for PERDA implementation because the West Halmahera community is a society dominated by the Sahu Tribe. The Sahu tribe is one of the tribes that adhere to the customs of the ancestors and is still preserved to this day. In addition to the cultural theme, the concept of implementing FTJ also departed from the historical reality that West Halmahera is one of the bases of Spice Islands in Indonesia. This shows that the local culture of the community smells of spices, as can be seen from the *sasadu orum* ritual which is conducted after harvest. The drafting of this implementation concept determines the policy at the FTJ PERDA Implementation stage. Themes based on culture give birth to cultural-based activity programs. So that FTJ West Halmahera which has been implemented for one decade makes culture as the primary color in the implementation of the year event. In the FTJ PERDA Implementation process, community involvement is needed because FTJ is not only a tourism event but also as a venue for the revival of local culture. Many benefits will be gained in the implementation of the FTJ, one of which is the economic benefits that will occur during the implementation of FTJ and even the implementation of FTJ. The concept of planning is needed in the initial stages of the PERDA

implementation. The quality of Human Resources (HR) in the Office of Tourism is very much needed in the formulation of the PERDA Implementation concept in the implementation of FTJ. HR is the key to the success of FTJ PERDA Implementation.

2. Partnership Development

The Partnership has principles in its implementation, and there are three important principles in the partnership, namely; first, Equality or balance (equity); The approach is not top down or bottom up, it is not only based on power but a relationship of mutual respect, mutual respect and trust. To avoid antagonism, it is necessary to build mutual trust. Equality includes the existence of rewards, obligations, and ties. Second, Transparency is needed to prevent mutual suspicion between partners. Provides transparency in information management and transparency in financial management. Third, the mutual benefit where a partnership must bring benefits to all parties involved. In this study, two parties become partners in the Implementation of the Regional Regulation of the FTJ, namely the private sector and the central and regional governments. The intent and purpose of the partnership is a "win-win solution partnership". Awareness and mutual benefit do not mean that the participants in the partnership must have the same abilities and strengths, but what is more important is the existence of equal bargaining positions based on their respective roles. Based on the cultural approach, partnerships aim to enable partners to adopt new values in implementing PERDA implementation such as HR expansion, destination arrangement, facility development, and promotion.

3. Community Capacity

The Jailolo Bay Festival is a tourism promotion event for West Halmahera. In this context, the development of a variety of tourist attractions has become an obligation in the tourism industry, because there are three primary keys to the progress of tourist destinations, namely attractions, accessibility and amenities (3A). These three components must be well developed and be a determinant of the success of a festival such as FTJ. Tourists visit FTJ in hopes of seeing the available tourism potential. The West Halmahera Tourism Office develops tourist attractions both cultural tourism, historical tourism and nature tourism as well as providing 16 tourism villages that continue to improve to present maximum attractions to tourists. Sasadu's house is a traditional Sahu tribe house in West Halmahera. The simple home, made of wood, construction with woven sago leaves as a roof. This traditional house has a definite cultural meaning in all aspects of its construction. The socio-cultural life of the tribal Sahu community was also held at this traditional house. This traditional house is used as a place to celebrate Thanksgiving parties for abundant harvests as well as being a place for citizens to gather, dine, dance together and share old values and local wisdom that are consistently adhered to in their daily lives. This traditional house has an essential meaning in the presence of the tribal Sahu community.

Figure 1. Traditional Halmahera Sahu (Sasadu) Tribal House

Sasadu's house does not use nails or screws that connect one beam/pillar to another but uses natural material from the earth of West Halmahera. This house has a roof ridge that towers on both ends depending on two rounds wrapped in palm fiber. This traditional house has no walls on the six sides of the building. All sides of the building are the entrance. This is the meaning of openness and hospitality of the Sahu tribe who are ready to welcome anyone who comes to their territory. Inside the Sasadu house, there are many carvings in the form of human feet, fish, and human faces which are many relief conditions that are meaningful. Sasadu has two ends of a carved wooden roof shaped like a bow and stem of the boat placed at both ends. Related symbolizes the boat that is sailing. The Sahu tribe itself is one of the tribes who like to cruise and adventure across the ocean. Replica of sailboats is also placed inside this traditional house called *kagunga tego-tego* (warships on land). The lowest roof position of the sasadu house is quite small. Anyone who wants to enter the sasadu house must lower and lower the body which gives the meaning of respect to the creator, for the tribe of the sahu sasadu tribe is a form of appreciation for women. In the room, there were two tables, one unique table for women on the front and one table for men in the back. Placing the women's desk in front implies that for the Sahu tribe women will take precedence and men always protect it from behind. Orom Sasadu or (traditional feast) West Halmahera Regency is a form of gratitude for the blessings received from the creator to the farmers during the abundant harvest. Orom Sasadu was always carried out at the house of the tribe of the sahu after the harvest of agricultural products was finished.

Figure 2. The Orom Sasadu Indigenous Dinner Party of the Sahu West Halmahera Tribe

This traditional ceremony is carried out for nine days and nine nights, seven days and seven nights, five days and five nights, three days and three nights or just one day night, depending on the yield obtained. There is three uniqueness in this traditional feast, that is, during partying they never sleep even though they don't sleep, never full also though they eat continuously and never get drunk even though they drink traditional drinks containing alcohol which in their local language is called *Saguwer*. During this traditional feast, there was never a fight between fellow traditional party organizers. This tradition is essential for tribal Sahu people because in traditional rituals it contains a lot of values and traditions which include a sense of brotherhood, the value of cooperation and an expression of gratitude to God Almighty. Orom Sasadu is one of the Sahu tribal identities as an agrarian society, and if the ceremony is not carried out, it is believed that it will not bring fortune to the life of the next farmer. The equipment needed to carry out the Orom Sasadu procession is musical instruments in the form of gongs, tifa and kenong to accompany Legu Salai and Saradabidabi dances. Some traditional food and drinks typical of the sahu tribe are also prepared such as twin rice, cala rice, processed fish, eggplant, mouse cap, *saguwer*, and others. Especially for West Halmahera Regency, which is one of the traditional agricultural systems that can still be found today. Paddy whose planting age is between 365 - 380 days. The planting procession which requires cultural work together. It is this spirit of cooperation that is the soul of the rice farm. From the first time planting seeds to harvest and the Waleng ceremony as a post-harvest party, it is always done together. In the past, the rice farming system in North Maluku also took place in Galela, North Halmahera and Makian Island of South Halmahera, so that from each of these places rice was known as Sahu Rice, Galela Rice, and Makian Rice. In the North Maluku rice farm, there are known types of local rice, namely *Kapuraca* (a type of sizeable rounded rice seed, emits a strong calf smell, and has a planting period of 6 months), *Kayoan* (also has 6 months of planting with large grains), woody (6 months of planting), *Jongodi/Dingodi* (small grains with a planting period of 3 months, and is the most delicious type of all types), as well as 2 varieties of glutinous rice which also grow for 6 months. Likewise, traditional equipment is used, for example is the rice cutting tool that is known in Sahu as *utu-utu*. The abundance of crops stored in a barn which the community is known as *Titila* and the remainder of the rice that has not yet been crushed are stored in a bamboo called *Gogoru* and will be presented to guests by pounding it in a soft mortar. Legu Salai dance is a dance that is performed from generation to generation by the ancestors of the Sahu tribe. This dance developed long before the establishment of the house of the clan of the Sahu tribe, the Sasadu house. Legu Salai dance is performed to welcome guests of the Sultanate or when celebrating a thanksgiving party during the harvest. Legu Salai dance is performed by three to seven male dancers (legu dancers), following the number of road cleaning work groups for the princess who will pass, which in Sahu's language is called *Jl'o Sahu Tala Re Pad'i*. When dancing, a group of male dancers will hold an umbrella symbolizing a protective figure for female dancers. Legu dancers also express high morale and working spirit through active and beautiful movements. The four female dancers (Salai dancers) symbolized the four sultanates on the earth Moloku Kie Raha. The four dancers danced with cheerful facial expressions as a symbol of joy for

receiving clothes from the Sultan. This strong interaction between Legu Salai dancers also symbolizes compassion, love for fellow human beings without differentiating between one another. Saradabidabi dance comes from Gamtala Village, West Halmahera Regency. This dance means arranging blades for the board to form a boat. Initially, this sacred dance was performed in welcoming ceremonies and opening ceremonial events in West Halmahera. Now, this dance is also performed during the opening of official functions and welcoming of important figures who come to West Halmahera. Saradabidabi dance was created based on community legend in West Halmahera. At one time, a princess at the time was prolonged crying, and no one could comfort and stop her crying. Seeing the condition of the Sultan became confused and made a contest to the community to create a dance to entertain the princess. Some dances were shown, but the princess never stopped crying. Until the turn, the Gamtala Village community presented a dance with the sound of loud gongs beginning to entertain the princess. Some dances were displayed, but the princess never stopped her crying. Until the turn of the Gamtala Village community to present a dance with the sound of the loud gongs echoing, suddenly the princess stopped her crying. The Sultan became happy and gave the name of this dance saradabidabi. Tata Ruba is a musical instrument made from one bamboo segment which is lifted by its skin to form a kind of string, and the bottom is given a hole as a resonator to produce a stronger sound. The bamboo skins that are raised into strings are divided into several types of sounds to produce sounds like tifa and gongs. It is estimated that this Ruba musical instrument emerged in the Neolithic era as a means of attaining ritual forms aimed at fertility and safety. In the Sahu tribal community in West Halmahera, this Ruba music is performed at traditional parties such as harvest parties and traditional feasts. According to the story that developed in the tribe of the Sahu tribe, the Ruba system was introduced in the colonial era as a ritual, so that the activity could still be carried out. It is estimated that this Ruba music instrument emerged after the Neolithic period as a means of achieving ritual forms aimed at fertility and safety. Manuru is a group of bamboo musical instrument players from Idaham Dehe Village, West Halmahera. This instrument is played in the assembly which is played by blowing.

Figure 3. Manuru Bamboo Music Attractions

From the form of rhythm, it can be seen that this music is influenced a lot by western (Dutch) music. This can be heard

from the rhythms delivered such as tango, waltz and cha-cha. Manuru bamboo music is displayed at ceremonial events such as picking up government guests and traditional guests. But now this instrument is also often played at brides' accompaniments or as entertainment for guests. According to Law No. 10 (2009) concerning Tourism, it is stated that tourism development is needed to encourage equal opportunities for business and benefit and that the community can face the challenges of changing the local, national and global life. For this reason, community participation is important to ensure that tourism development runs sustainably and the community is expected to get the maximum benefit from tourism activities in the area. Green tourism also opens economic opportunities for the community, especially if done using local resources such as transportation, accommodation and guide services. To achieve better service, tourism income can be allocated to develop the capacity of the management community by increasing the type of business or cultural attractions that will be displayed. Besides, the activities of planting values to preserve the environment are things that should not be forgotten in community empowerment activities [11]. Community participation will arise due to direct benefits from the environment around tourism. To be able to provide benefits, the situation must be maintained. It is a reciprocal relationship between tourism activities, management and interests obtained from the environment around tourism. If nature is preserved, then the people themselves will enjoy the sustainability. Likewise with tourism activities, if the preservation of the environment around the tourism area is well maintained, then the people who will benefit economically [11]. Therefore, in the concept of empowerment, so that people want to participate in tourism activities that do not damage the environment there are three components that must exist, namely; 1) enabling setting, namely strengthening the situation in the tourism area including the facilities and infrastructure needed so that the community can be creative; 2) Empowering local communities, namely increasing the knowledge and skills of local communities through education, training and various other forms of development; 3) Socio-political support, namely the need for social support, political support, networking by the local government, Tourism Office and other supporting elements. In this context, the involvement of the community in the implementation of the FTJ PERDA is very diverse and has a very direct impact on the community itself, such as the birth of 16 community-based tourism villages, the construction of destinations, most of which are self-help by utilizing village funds provided by the village ministry every year. Community involvement, one of which is the provision of accommodation such as lodging, hotels, restaurants, to homestays. The number of hotels/inns in West Halmahera Regency during 2012 was recorded at 11 units. The hotels/inns are spread among others in Jailolo and South Jailolo Districts. The number of rooms available is 146 rooms with beds totaling 154 beds. Guests staying numbered 3,682 people with a total of 3,591 Indonesian citizens and the rest are foreigners. The restaurant became one of the accommodation support services in West Halmahera Regency. During 2012 there were 26 houses. Food stalls in West Halmahera Regency. Jailolo Sub-district has the most significant number of restaurants, as many as 15 units or 57 per cent of all restaurants in West Halmahera Regency. In addition to hotels, inns and restaurants in Jailolo there is also a homestay that has existed since the FTJ was held.

Homestay is a home for tourists who use residents' homes. The purpose of using this homestay is so that tourists can interact with local people. The existence of a homestay also has a direct impact on the local community so that the presence of tourism in the economic impact is not only felt by the investors, namely the owners of hotels, restaurants, or inns but also felt directly by the local community.

Table 2. Number of Homestay in West Halmahera

Villages	Number of Homestay	Number of Rooms
Desa Siokonora	34	52
Desa Guemaadu	21	25
Desa Jalan Baru	3	4
Desa Gofasa	7	10
Desa Idamdehe	10	12
Desa Guaria	12	15

Table 2 above, shows that the availability of homestay is also quite maximum. According to Fenny Kiat, the existence of this homestay will continue to grow, and in the future, an organization will be formed to empower homestay owners. The presence of the restaurant mentioned above is increasing in number because the impact of tourism development is felt directly by the local community of West Halmahera. The role or involvement of the community is the main key to the success of tourism development in West Halmahera.

4. Fund Availability

Private parties such as BRI provide funding sources in tourism development as a manifestation of the PERDA FTJ Implementation. BRI's involvement in the event of destinations, because of a sense of concern in creating the prosperity of rural communities who have a full desire for the development of the tourism sector. In 2018, BRI Bank provided funding assistance for the development of the Bobanehena tourism village as much as IDR 400,000,000 for the procurement of homestay facilities above the sea and the construction of the Lappa Pelangi beach tourism gate. This assistance shows that the FTJ PERDA has the full support of the private sector to create the prosperity of the local community. In addition to development funding sources from the private sector, the role of PEMDA West Halmahera is certainly large enough in the development of Travel Destinations in the Implementation of FTJ every year, and the Regional Government must spend as much as IDR. 1 billion for the success of the annual event. Likewise with aid funds from the Ministry of Tourism and the Ministry of Villages for tourist destinations such as tourist villages that are building.

Table 3. Name of hotel, number of rooms in West Halmahera Regency

Name of Hotel / Lodging	Address	Number of Rooms
Hotel D'Hoek	Jl. Raya Hatebicara	55
Villa Sabua Gaba	Jl. Guaemaadu,	7
Penginapan Camar	Jl. Gufasa, Jailolo	17
Penginapan Nusantara Indah	Jl. Gufasa, Jailolo	14
Pondok Saloi	Desa Tedeng	10
Penginapan Namila Indah	Jl. Ki Hajar	12
Penginapan Melati	Dewantara	6
Penginapan Mari Sayang	Jl. Gufasa	8
Penginapan Amboina	Desa Porniti	10
Penginapan Sidangoli Indah	Desa Porniti	14
Penginapan Wosa Ino	Desa Sidangoli	10
	Desa Domato	

Supporting Factors and Obstacle of FTJ Implementation Strategy (PERDA No 2 (2012) at the West Halmahera Tourism Office

Supporting factors for implementation are as follows; a) the availability of the budget to implement programs and activities derived from the funds of the West Halmahera Regional Budget (APBD) and the Ministry of Tourism Fund. For 2018, FTJ has been included as one of the Festivals in Indonesia's 100 Top Event festivals. So that in 2018, FTJ will get funding assistance from the Ministry of Tourism; b) the wealth of tourism potential possessed by West Halmahera in the form of tourist attraction spread throughout the West Halmahera region, supported by natural wealth, diverse cultures and histories that are still maintained; c) the availability of tourism facilities and infrastructure in West Halmahera which are very numerous and varied, and always increase every year due to the needs of tourists. Especially the tourism supporting facilities, the existence of other facilities that continue to be improved such as tour packages and TIC (Tourist Information Center); d) the stable social and security conditions in West Halmahera are shown by the views of tourists towards West Halmahera which is considered as the center of Moloku Kie Raha's global culture with the people known for being friendly, polite and having a high concern for their culture and environment; and 5) the support of the West Halmahera community towards the implementation of FTJ is very maximum. It is necessary to sharpen the management of the community's spirit to become the strength of FTJ in the future.

Table 4. Name and Address of Restaurants in West Halmahera Regency

Restaurant Name	Address
Restauran Soa Konora	Desa Soakonora, Jailolo
MP M. Puteri Jaya	Desa Gufasa, Jailolo
M. Puteri Jaya Miesa	Hatebicara, Jailolo
RM. Minang Saiy	Desa Gufasa, Jailolo
RM. Ampera	Desa Gufasa, Jailolo
RM. Ica Jelita	Jl. Jati Soakonora, Jailolo
RM. Subur	Jl. Raya Hatebicara, Jailolo
I RM. Amazy ChickenjW Crispy	Hatebicara, Desa Gufasa, Jailolo
RM. Popeda Jailoll.	Desa Gufasa, Jailolo
RM. Ojolali	Jl. Jati Soakonora, Jailolo
RM. Lapangan Ter.	Desa Hatebicara, Jailolo
RM. Novaldo	Desa Hatebicara, Jailolo
RM. Handayani	Sangoli Gam, Jailolo Selatan
RM. Mari Sayan	Desa Domato, Jailolo Selatan
RM. Mika hma Saya MI	Desa Hatebicara, Jailolo
RM. Dapur Alam	Desa Dodinga, Jailolo Selatan
RM. Ladeni	Desa Dum-Dum, Jailolo Timur
RM. Dodinga	Desa Dodinga, Jailolo Selatan
RM. Sari Laut Yulia 99	Hatebicara Jailolo
RM. Goyang Lidah	Hatebicara Jailolo

While the implementation inhibiting factor consists of; a) human resources or apparatus owned by the West Halmahera Tourism Office is inadequate regarding quantity and quality. Regarding quantity, the number of employees of the West Halmahera Tourism Office has not met the standards of HR requirements of the apparatus that has been set, so that it cannot work optimally. In addition to the number that has not supported, in quality, the apparatus resources owned by the West Halmahera Tourism Office are also many who are not specific experts in the field of tourism, so that in the realm of administrative willingness is quite a maximal service, but in the domain of concepts there are still shortcomings, and this must be fulfilled so the quality of developing destinations in West

Halmahera in the future can be realized; b) less than optimal cooperation between stakeholders, including the government, the private sector, and the community, especially in developing the number of new tourism packages and products offered to tourists as well as the lack of investors who want to invest in West Halmahera. So that there are so many destinations that have world-class attractions such as Kahatola and Mariporoco waterfalls in Loloda that have yet to be developed; d) aware of tourism among the people of West Halmahera is still low. This can be seen from the unpreparedness of the people in the village in welcoming FTJ. Villagers in the vicinity of the FTJ location do not allow homerooms to be used as homestays, so there are only a few houses that are used as homestays; and d) in the development of destinations for FTJ readiness, there are still groups that fight both on behalf of landowners and resistance in the form of criticism of the lack of involvement of local communities. This inhibiting factor can only be solved if the awareness of the local community can be built correctly. This awareness can be developed with training and guidance for tourism conscious development and community involvement in preparing tourist destinations or attractions. If this is done, then the feeling of belonging to FTJ is created as part of their daily habits.

5 CONCLUSIONS

The potential of marine wealth that can be developed into tourism commodities in the Indonesian sea include business tourism (business tourism), beach tourism (seaside tourism), cultural tourism (cruise tourism), cruise tourism, nature tourism (eco-tourism) and sports tourism. For marine tourism to be sustainable, the products displayed must be under the local environment. Thus the local community will care about the tourism resources they have because it provides direct benefits, so they feel tourism activities as a whole in their lives. There are problems in the field, in the form of developing destination aspects, providing human tourism resources, full community involvement, so that PEMDA West Halmahera still dominates the implementation of FTJ. These deficiencies should have been resolved because FTJ 2018 has entered a decade. The management should have matured as a people's festival. On the other hand, to measure the impact caused by the implementation of FTJ, which spent 1 billion in each implementation, it can be seen from the level of the visit during FTJ implementation that was booming during the peak event because the tourism service brought in artists who were top artists. Seeing this, the West Halmahera Regency government should begin to reform every program carried out, in the sense that a successful program must continue to be maintained and make the latest innovations to support and sustain the successful program. While plans that have not been successful (infrastructure development) must be changed both in planning and in the implementation of the program so that the tourism infrastructure that is still minimal is currently developing to support the objectives of the FTJ PERDA in West Halmahera Regency.

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